

THE EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT ON THE WEAR AND FRICTION OF SHORT GLASS-FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES IN UNLUBRICATED ROLLING-SLIDING CONTACT

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ABSTRACT

The effects of reinforcement on the wear and friction of short glass-fibre reinforced polyamide-66 composites running against each other, in unlubricated, non-conformal, rolling-sliding contact have been investigated. These composites show complex wear and friction properties because an initial thin film exists on the contact surfaces when two discs run against each other under these test conditions. The film plays a dominant role in the "self-lubricating" property of the composite. The formation and life of the film on the composite have been studied. It is suggested that the "self-lubricating" property could be applied in engineering components.

INTRODUCTION

Short-fibre reinforced polymer composites are now being used increasingly as engineering materials because of their high strength-to-weight ratio and ease of manufacture linked to good tribological properties [1-5]. Non-conformal engineering components made from injection moulded composites are a major application area and typically include gears, cams and rolling element bearings. However, relatively little research into the wear mechanisms of these polymer composites running against themselves has been carried out.

Most applications simply use identical materials for both surfaces because of the design convenience in limiting the range of materials [6-11]. Wear tests which only consider conformal sliding contact (e.g. pin-on-disc tests) [16-18] simply do not match either non-conformal rolling-sliding contact nor identical materials in contact [19-21]. It is, therefore, very difficult to interpret the wear mechanisms of polymer composite gears [10-15] and to improve the performance of polymer composites in such applications. It is essential that tests are conducted under the appropriate conditions of unlubricated, non-conformal, rolling-sliding contact in order to establish the effects of reinforcement on the wear and friction of short-glass fibre reinforced polymer composites.

EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS AND PROCEDURE

The twin-disc wear testing machine used in our previous work [13-15] was again employed in this investigation. With this machine, measurements of both the frictional force and wear (as a change in radius) between two discs in contact can be made continuously. Experiments were carried out either at different slip ratios under a given normal load or at different loads with a given slip ratio. Both the loading and sliding conditions of engineering components such as gears, cams and bearings in non-conformal, rolling-sliding contact can be simulated by this method [13-15, 22].

The material used was short-glass fibre reinforced polyamide-66 (PA66). The proportions of glass fibre added were 40 wt% (LNP grade RF1008) and 30 wt% respectively [3]. The specimens from RF1008 were moulded by Davall Moulded Gears Ltd and those from 30% wt. short-glass fibre PA66 composites were prepared by machining from extruded bar. Both were polished to a surface roughness below 1.5 μm . Both the top and bottom discs were 30 mm diameter and 10 mm facewidth.

Tests were run at rolling speeds of 1000 rpm and a range of loads and slip ratios. Slip ratio is defined here as the ratio of sliding to rolling velocities and varies from 0 for pure rolling to 1.0 for simple sliding with one disc stationary. In mathematical form, if the surface velocities are v_1 and v_2 then the sliding velocity is $(v_1 - v_2)$ and the rolling velocity is $(v_1 + v_2)/2$.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Typical wear and friction results for moulded 30 wt% glass-filled PA 66 composites are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Real-time measurements of wear and coefficient of friction at 0.11 slip ratio, 300 N normal load and 1000 rpm

The wear was measured here as the separation of the disc centres. After bedding-in, the wear profile consisted of three regions: a nearly constant one; a very short unstable region and a near-linear wear phase with a period of significantly increasing wear. During the first period the wear curve was very flat and little wear was exhibited - wear debris could hardly be observed and the contact surfaces of the two discs appeared to become more and more polished. There appeared to be a film over the contact surfaces which covered the glass fibres and caused the polished appearance.

The second period was relatively short no matter how high the slip ratio and corresponded to the surface film peeling with wear debris being detached from the surface. Following this film-peeling phase, the wear increased sharply and more and more wear debris was detached. Once the film had been completely removed the wear entered the severe wear region in which the wear was so high that it caused eventual destruction. In the severe wear region the wear was more sensitive to slip ratio than to load. In contrast, the friction coefficient μ in the severe wear region of this material was more sensitive to load than to slip ratio.

The majority of material loss was in the severe wear region. This was where the thin surface layer had been disrupted and the wear rate was dominated by the ability or otherwise of this film to be formed continuously during wear and to be retained on the surface. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed this suggestion. Fig. 2 shows the wear and friction coefficients as a function of number of cycles for several different slip ratios.

Fig.2 Wear and coefficients of friction of 40% short glass-fibre reinforced PA 66 composite at 1000 rpm and 300 N normal load

Fig. 3 is an SEM micrograph of the initial surface, machined and polished for tests. It can be seen that most fibres are uncovered and oriented randomly. In Fig. 4, taken during the first 'non-wear' period, it can be seen that there is a layer of film which covers or partly covers the fibres and the proportion of fibres on the surface is generally greater than that seen initially. This suggests that the proportion of fibres beneath the surface layer increases until the film peels off and produces a fibre-rich sub-surface. The thickness of the surface film varied typically from 2 to 5 μm .

Fig.3 An SEM image of an initial specimen surface machined and polished for tests

Fig.4 Contact surface in the "non-wear" region at a slip ratio of 0.04, normal load of 300 N and running speed of 1000 rpm

The degree of fibre orientation on the surface was strongly affected by the slip ratio. When the slip ratio reached 0.28 with 300 N load and at 1000 rpm the fibres on the surface were highly aligned, as shown in Fig. 5, and approximately parallel to the friction force. Fig. 5 also indicates

that both long and short broken fibres can move on the surface causing alignment from an initially random distribution. However, for RF1008, the aligned broken fibres do not remain on the surface indefinitely. As the film peeled, they were either expelled out as debris or rebedded into the PA66 matrix beneath them.

Fig.5 Broken and aligned fibres on the worn surfaces after disruption of the thin film (28.6% slip ratio, 300 N normal load and 1000 rpm)

DISCUSSION

It is suggested that the thin surface film plays a dominant role in the "self-lubricating" property of the composite. With this film on the surface, the composite can be protected so significantly that little wear debris can be found and the wear cannot be measured with a transducer to an accuracy of $1\mu\text{m}$. The wear rate determined by weighing is around $10^{-6}\mu\text{m}/\text{cycle}$ and the friction coefficient μ can be below 0.1. On the other hand, once this layer has been removed from the contact surfaces, the "self-lubricating" property is destroyed and the wear rate increases sharply to about $10^{-4}\mu\text{m}/\text{cycle}$ and μ can increase threefold up to 0.3. This phenomenon in glass fibre reinforced PA 66 is similar to that in other polymer composites [24]. However, in contrast to Lancaster's suggestion [24], this self-lubricating property does not offer merely temporary protection but may remain for over 10^7 cycles if fibre concentration, thermal history, load and slip ratio can be controlled properly.

Two possibilities for the formation of the film are suggested. One is that fibres are rebedded deeper and deeper in the polymer matrix until they become covered with polyamide film. This is limited by fibre concentration. Under the same test conditions the wear rate of the composite with 40% glass fibre is higher by a factor of two than that of the same composite with 30% glass fibres. Such a large difference in wear rate could be due to the lifetime of the self-lubricating film. The film in the former material lasted for only about 6.0×10^5 cycles but that of the latter

one lasted for over 4.0×10^6 cycles without any indication of the film peeling. It is suggested that high-fibre concentration polyamide can easily cause disruption of the self-lubricating film since there is less room for the fibres to be bedded into the matrix.

The other possibility is that the matrix material around the fibres is stretched or smeared on to the counter-surface. This possibility has been studied by changing the crystallinity of the composites while keeping fibre concentration constant at 30%. Bar A has a percentage crystallinity of 27% as measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) but the crystallinity of bar B is 45%. The associated difference in stiffness of the matrix material is about 100%, and in yield stress is approximately 40% [25].

The wear rate of bar A with lower crystallinity is only just above 10^{-6} $\mu\text{m}/\text{cycle}$ and that of bar B with higher crystallinity has reached 4.0×10^{-5} $\mu\text{m}/\text{cycle}$. It is suggested that it is more difficult for fibres to bed into the PA 66 matrix with the higher stiffness. Unbedded fibres may act as hard asperities on the contact surfaces and abrasive wear is inevitable. It again appears that such a large difference in wear rates is due to the life of the thin surface film. For the sample with lower crystallinity the film lasted over 4.0×10^6 cycles without significant disruption. For the sample of bar B with higher crystallinity the life of the film on the wear surface was only 6.0×10^5 cycles.

Once the film layer has been worn away the wear in the 'severe wear' region is considerably higher than the original value but is nevertheless lower than that obtained for unreinforced polyamide [15]. The wear in this region is very dependent on material properties - both fibre content and percentage crystallinity of the matrix material. It is higher for 40% reinforcement compared with 30%.

CONCLUSIONS

The polyamide 66 composite shows complex wear and friction properties. Both the coefficient of friction and the wear rate are very low under a wide range of loads and slip ratios. The high resistance to wear and friction of this composite results from its significant "self-lubricating" property. A layer of a thin film exits on the contact surfaces when two discs run against each other under these test conditions. It is this thin film that plays a dominant role in the "self-lubricating" property of the composite. With the separation of the contact surfaces by this film, the wear rate of the composite is rather low and in the range of 10^{-6} $\mu\text{m}/\text{cycle}$ and the friction coefficient m is below 0.1. However, once this layer has been removed, the "self-lubricating" property is destroyed so that the wear rate increases sharply by an approximate factor of two to 10^{-4} - 10^{-3} $\mu\text{m}/\text{cycle}$ while the friction coefficient m is below 0.28-0.35.

The formation of the thin film and the life of the short-glass fibre reinforced polyamide 66 depend on structure, strength and fibre concentration, as well as on the loads and slip ratios. A single wear coefficient [23] is inadequate to represent the behaviour and accelerated testing is unable to provide sufficient data. It is necessary to test these composites over long time periods under conditions which closely match service conditions.

Under identical loading conditions, either lower fibre concentration or crystallinity cause the film to form continuously so that the life of the film on the contact surfaces may reach 6×10^6 - 10^7 cycles. The life of this thin film is so great that it should not be treated as a temporary phenomenon during the "running-in" period and it is reasonable to suggest that this self-lubricating period can be used during the normal working life of engineering components. A fibre rich layer beneath the thin film is also formed during the wear process in short glass fibre-filled polyamide 66. This fibre-rich layer plays a vital role in supporting part of the applied load and reducing the wear rate of the matrix material in the severe wear region.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K Friedrich, *Advances in Composite Tribology*, p.109, (Elsevier, London, 1993).
- [2] L A Carlsson, *Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, p.103, (Elsevier, Oxford, 1991).
- [3] LNP Engineering Plastics Inc, *A Guide to LNP's Internal Lubricated Thermoplastics*, (LNP, USA 1994).
- [4] M J Folkes, *Short Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastics*, p.1, (Wiley, Chichester, 1982).
- [5] H Voss and K Friedrich, *Wear*, **116**, 1, (1987).
- [6] British Standard BS 6168, *Specification for Non-metallic Spur Gears*, (BSI, London, 1987)
- [7] *Polypenco Gear Design*, (Polypenco Corporation, USA, 1985).
- [8] Engineering Science Data Unit, *Design of Parallel Axis Straight Spur and Helical Gears*, (Engineering Science Data Unit, 1987).
- [9] R J Drago, *Fundamentals of Gear Design*, (Butterworths, Boston, 1988).
- [10] C J Hooke, K Mao, D Walton, A R Breeds, S N Kukureka, *ASME Journal of Tribology*, **115**, 119, (1993).
- [11] A R Breeds, S N Kukureka, K Mao, D Walton and C J Hooke, *Wear*, **166**, 85, (1993).
- [12] Y Yamaguchi, *Tribology of Plastic Materials*, (Elsevier, New York, 1990).
- [13] Y K Chen, *Tribology of polymers and composites in unlubricated rolling and sliding contact*, MPhil thesis, The University of Birmingham, (1993).
- [14] S N Kukureka, Y K Chen, C J Hooke and P Liao, *Proceedings of the 1994 International Gearing Conference, Newcastle*, (ed. J N Fawcett, MEP, London, 1994).
- [15] S N Kukureka, Y K Chen, C J Hooke and P Liao, *Wear*, (in press).
- [16] K Tanaka and Y Uchiyama, In L H Lee ed., *Advances in polymer friction and Wear*, **5B**, p499, (Plenum, New York, 1974).
- [17] J K Lancaster, *Tribology*, **6**, 219, (1972).
- [18] K Tanaka, *ASME Journal of Lubrication Technology*, **99**, 408, (1977).
- [19] M Clerico, *Wear*, **13**, 183, (1969).
- [20] M Clerico, *Wear*, **64**, 259, (1980).
- [21] M Clerico and V Patierno, *Wear*, **53**, 279, (1979).
- [22] P J Guichear, Bernard S Levy and N M Parikh, *Gear Manufacture and Performance*, (American Society for Metals, Ohio, USA, 1974).
- [23] J F Archard, *Journal of Applied Physics*, **24**, 981, (1953).
- [24] J K Lancaster, *Proceedings of the 8th Leeds-Lyon Symposium on Tribology*, p33, (ed. Dowson et al, Butterworth, London, 1982).
- [25] Howard W Starkweather, JR, George E Moore, John E Hansen, Thomas M Roder and Richard E Brooks, *Journal of Polymer Science*, **XXI**, 189, (1956).

